

ABSORPTION BASED CO₂ CAPTURE USING KOH SOLUTION COUPLED WITH ELECTROCHEMICAL REGENERATION CELL: PROCESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

While most of the industrial scale CO₂ capture installations are currently using amine-based solutions, there are significant environmental concerns due to the high heat demand for solvent regeneration and emissions of amines or their degradation products. Instead, alkaline solvents have been studied as an alternative owing to their high absorption efficiency and their negligible volatility [1]. Meanwhile, several studies have previously discussed the possibility of using electrochemical regeneration for a number of solvents including potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) [1], sodium hydroxide (NaOH) [2], lithium hydroxide (LiOH) [3] and potassium hydroxide (KOH) [4]. These novel technologies can be driven by renewable electricity, thus contributing to the goal of reaching the net-zero targets set by the European Green Deal. This paper presents the model development of a carbon capture pilot plant based on CO₂ absorption with KOH solution and the subsequent solvent regeneration in an electrochemical cell (EC) configuration. In the first part of the process, the flue gas entering the column reacts with the lean KOH solvent flowing counter-currently and the CO₂ present in the stream gets absorbed in the alkaline solvent to form potassium carbonate and bicarbonate. The clean gas then leaves the column while the rich solvent heads towards the EC where a pH shift facilitates the CO₂ desorption via the introduction of protons in the EC anode. This leads to a change in the equilibrium state and the removal of the majority of CO₂ in the membrane contactor. The remaining solution then heads towards the cathode of the EC where the solvent gets regenerated, i.e, hydroxide ions are added via the cathode to recombine with lone potassium cations.

The process model consists of two parts, a rate-based CO₂ capture module, modelled in Aspen Plus and an equilibrium-based regeneration module, modelled in Matlab. The model was validated against literature data [2] and new lab data produced in the ConsenCUS project, while the process performance was evaluated by tracking key indicators for both units. Using the validated model, process simulations for several flue gas and lean solvent compositions were performed considering

an upscaled (at pilot scale) version of the model. Finally, a parametric analysis was done to assess the effect of different process input parameters on the model output and to determine the optimal conditions for running the process.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the process

Figure 2: Example results from the equilibrium-based regeneration model, for a rich solvent loading of 0.64 (left) and 1 (right), for different load ratios, and for different concentrations of KOH. The figures present the specific electrical energy consumption (SEEC) in $[kJ mol^{-1}]$. A background electrolyte was always present, here, K_2SO_4 at 0.05 molal concentration.

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ConsenCUS

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Rahimi, G. Catalini, S. Hariharan, M. Wang, M. Puccini, and T. A. Hatton, “Carbon Dioxide Capture Using an Electrochemically Driven Proton Concentration Process,” *Cell Reports Phys. Sci.*, vol. 1, no. 4, p. 100033, 2020.
- [2] Q. Shu, L. Legrand, P. Kuntke, M. Tedesco, and H. V. M. Hamelers, “Electrochemical Regeneration of Spent Alkaline Absorbent from Direct Air Capture,” *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 54, no. 14, pp. 8990–8998, 2020.
- [3] S. Kim *et al.*, “Electrochemical recovery of LiOH from used CO₂ adsorbents,” *Catal. Today*, vol. 359, no. June, pp. 83–89, 2021.
- [4] F. Sabatino *et al.*, “Evaluation of a Direct Air Capture Process Combining Wet Scrubbing and Bipolar Membrane Electrodialysis,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 59, no. 15, pp. 7007–7020, 2020.